

A historical perspective of Tian's evolution algebras

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Abstract

Even if it has been less than a decade and a half since Tian introduced his concept of evolution algebras to represent algebraically non-Mendelian rules in Genetics, their study is becoming increasingly widespread mainly due to their applications to many scientific disciplines. In order to facilitate further research on the topic, this paper deals with the past and present research on these kind of algebras, together with the most relevant topics regarding them.

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1. Introduction

2 Dealing with the chloroplast inheritance in plants, the German botanists
3 and geneticists Carl Correns (1864–1933) [32] [33] and Erwin Baur (1875–
4 1933) [6] realized the relevance that non-Mendelian rules have in Genetics.
5 In spite of this, and unlike Mendelian Genetics, for which an algebraic inter-
6 pretation of its rules was already introduced in the 1930's by Serebrowski [89]
7 and Kostitzin [63], it is not until the early 2000s that a similar interpretation
8 for non-Mendelian rules was proposed.

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9 More specifically, in order to relate Markov chains with the prokaryotic
10 cell reproduction, and based on the self-reproduction rules of non-Mendelian
11 Genetics, evolution algebras were firstly introduced in the Ph.D. Thesis of Jin
12 Jung Paul Tian [92] in 2004; then jointly presented with Petr Vojtechovsky
13 [98] in 2006, and later analyzed in greater depth in a book by Tian [93] in
14 2008. The dynamic nature of these non-associative algebras is not described
15 by a series of identities, unlike many other known non-associative algebras
16 such as alternative, Lie, Malcev or Jordan algebras, amongst others. More
17 specifically, an *evolution algebra* E over a field \mathbb{K} is a finite-dimensional algebra
18 such that there exists a *natural basis* $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ so that $e_i \cdot e_j = 0$, for all
19 $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $i \neq j$, and $e_i \cdot e_i = \sum_k p_{ik} e_k$, for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$,
20 and some coefficients $p_{ik} \in \mathbb{K}$, which are called the *structural constants* of
21 the evolution algebra E . This multiplication is extended linearly from the
22 given multiplication of basis elements. By considering each generator e_i as an
23 allele in Genetics, the *structure matrix* $(p_{ij})_{i,j}$ encodes somehow the laws of
24 inheritance of non-Mendelian Genetics as algebraic properties of the algebra.

25 Even if a wide range of mathematicians has dealt with this type of algebras
26 since the original manuscripts of Tian and Vojtechovsky, the relevance
27 of evolution algebras is not still widely known. In order to make easier
28 further research on the topic, this paper gathers together the antecedents,
29 origin, early stage and later development of this kind of algebras, and shows
30 different applications arising from them.

31 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 outlines the origin and de-
32 velopment of genetic algebras as primordial antecedents of Tian's concept of
33 evolution algebras. In Section 3 some preliminary concepts and results on
34 evolution algebras are indicated. Next, in each subsection of Section 4, a
35 brief comment on the main papers published on this topic is given. Further-
36 more, Section 5 overviews the relationship among evolution algebras, Graph
37 theory, Group theory, Markov chains and Biology. The paper is completed
38 with an extensive bibliography, which may be of valuable help to all those
39 researchers interested in this topic. Throughout the paper, we follow the
40 current notation, which may differ from the original one to which we refer.

41 2. Antecedents

42 This section deals with the origin of genetic algebras as cornerstone of
43 Tian's concept of evolution algebra. For more details about the historical
44 background on genetic algebras, we refer the reader to [12, 105, 67, 84].

45 In 1866, Gregor Johann Mendel (1822–1884) was the first who made use
46 of algebraic symbols to express sexual reproduction laws of inheritance. It
47 was done in his original manuscript on experiments in plant hybridization
48 [68]. More specifically, given a pair of plant characters **A** and **a**, together
49 with the hybrid form **Aa** in which both characters fuse together, Mendel
50 indicated with an expression of the form $\alpha\mathbf{A} + \beta\mathbf{Aa} + \gamma\mathbf{a}$ the ratio $\alpha : \beta : \gamma$
51 of numbers of offsprings having each possible plant character **A**, **Aa** and **a**
52 in the following generation. In this way, Mendel introduced three principles:

- 53 • The *principle of paired factors*, which states that characters are con-
54 trolled by unit factors that appear in pairs within each individual or-
55 ganism.
- 56 • The *principle of dominance*, which states that one of the two previous
57 factors is dominant and makes its effect in the individual, whereas the
58 other one is recessive and does not show its effect unless both characters
59 are recessive.
- 60 • The *principle of segregation*, which states that, during the inheritance
61 process, the mentioned pair of factors separate randomly so that the
62 offspring receives exactly one factor from each parent.

63 Almost forgotten for decades, Mendel’s laws were independently redis-
64 covered around 1900 by the Dutch botanist Hugo de Vries (1848–1935) [103],
65 who introduced the term *mutation* and suggested that of *gene*; the German
66 botanist and geneticist Carl Correns (1864–1933) [32], who discovered the
67 cell extranuclear inheritance; the Austrian agronomist Erich von Tschermak
68 (1871–1962) [101], who introduced the combination of plant characters in or-
69 der to improve the efficiency of plant breeding; and the American agronomist
70 William Jasper Spillman (1863–1931) [90], whose work was crucial for the
71 development of *Agricultural Economics*. The emergence of all their contribu-
72 tions concerning the distribution of characters among offspring in plant hy-
73 bridization made fundamental the study and development of Mendel’s laws.

74 In 1905, the English biologist William Bateson (1861–1926) introduced
75 the term *Genetics* to describe the study of inheritance processes [5]. Bateson
76 was a fervent advocate of Mendel [4], whose principles, even being reborn,
77 were questioned at that time. An interesting question in this regard had been
78 asked in 1902 by the British statistician George Udny Yule (1871–1951),
79 who contemplated [107] that dominant factors could increase indefinitely

80 in a continuous way throughout generations. One year later, the English
 81 mathematician and biostatistician Karl Pearson (1857–1936) [83] and the
 82 American zoologist and geneticist William Ernest Castle (1867–1962) [29]
 83 established that, under random circumstances, there exists certain stability of
 84 characters in the inheritance process. Concerning such a stability, the English
 85 mathematician Godfrey Harold Hardy (1877–1947) [51] asked in 1908 about
 86 the circumstances under which the distribution of characters in the offspring
 87 is the same that in the generation before in the absence of disturbing factors.

88 The answer was independently given at that moment by Hardy himself
 89 and the German physician Wilhelm Weinberg (1862–1937) [104], and is cur-
 90 rently known as the *Hardy-Weinberg law*. An important limitation of that law
 91 is the assumption of a potentially infinite population, not taking into account
 92 the importance of sampling fluctuations in evolutionary processes described
 93 by finite populations. The first proposal dealing with such a possibility would
 94 be the so-called *Wright-Fisher model* based on the original manuscripts of the
 95 American geneticist Sewall Green Wright (1889–1988) [106] and the British
 96 statistician and geneticist Ronald Aylmer Fisher (1890–1962) [44].

97 In 1923-24, the Soviet mathematician Sergei Natanovich Bernstein (1880-
 98 1968) [10, 11] introduced the concept of *quadratic stochastic operator* (QSO)
 99 as a map $V : S \rightarrow S$, where

$$S := \{(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n : x_i > 0, \text{ for all } i, \text{ and } \sum_i x_i = 1\},$$

100 and, for each $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in S$, it is $V((x_1, \dots, x_n)) = (V(x_1), \dots, V(x_n))$,
 101 where

$$V(x_k) := \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}^k x_i x_j, \text{ for all } k \in \{1, \dots, n\}.$$

102 Here, the product $x_i x_j$ is the usual product of real numbers. In addition,
 103 $p_{ij}^k \geq 0$ and $p_{ij}^k = p_{ji}^k$, for all $i, j, k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, and $\sum_k p_{ij}^k = 1$, for all
 104 $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. As such, every QSO constitutes an *evolutionary operator*
 105 that describes the time evolution or inheritance process of a *free population*
 106 with n different genetic types.

107 More specifically, each component x_i of a given element $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in$
 108 S represents the probability that a random individual in the population under
 109 consideration belongs to the species that is determined by the i^{th} genetic
 110 type. Hence, the n -tuple x describes the distribution of the population with
 111 respect to the n genetic types, whereas $V(x)$ describes such a distribution

112 for the next generation. In particular, each value $p_{ij}^k = p_{ji}^k$ determines the
 113 probability that an offspring with genetic type k arises from two individuals
 114 of respective genetic types i and j , without sexual differentiation.

115 Based on the possible fluctuation of genetic types throughout subsequent
 116 generations of an evolutionary process, a main problem in the theory of QSOs
 117 consists of determining their limit behavior for any given initial distribution
 118 of genetic types $x \in S$. That is, the study of the corresponding distribution
 119 $V^m(x)$ for the m^{th} generation, when m tends to infinity. In this regard,
 120 Bernstein focused in particular on the problem of determining and classifying
 121 all those QSOs for which a stationary distribution or stable evolution arises
 122 in only one generation (that is, such that $V^2 = V$). Even if Bernstein only
 123 solved this problem for $n = 3$, it is currently solved for all dimensions (see
 124 [49, 50]). To this end, it would be crucial the work in 1975 of Philip Holgate
 125 (1934–1993) [56], who expressed algebraically this problem as follows.

126 1. Firstly, Holgate related each given evolutionary operator V with the
 127 algebra described as

$$xy = \frac{1}{2} (V(x + y) - V(x) - V(y)).$$

128 (It was called *evolution algebra* by Joseph Bayara [7, 8], which differs
 129 from the concept introduced by Tian, the one that is commonly used
 130 in the current literature and with which this paper deals.)

131 2. Then, he introduced the concept of *Bernstein algebra* as an algebra
 132 A such that $x^2 x^2 = \omega^2(x) x^2$, for all $x \in A$, where ω is an algebra
 133 homomorphism from A into its base field, which is called the *weight*
 134 of the algebra. Recall that an algebra for which one such a non-trivial
 135 homomorphism exists is called *baric* [39].

136 In 1934, Alexander Pawlowitsch Serebrowski (1884-1938) [89] was the first
 137 to give an algebraic interpretation of the symbol \times as a mathematical way to
 138 represent Mendelian inheritance laws. A similar symbolic multiplication was
 139 independently introduced shortly after by Aleksandrovich Kostitzin (1883-
 140 1963) [63].

141 At the same period, Valery Ivanovich Glivenkov (1896-1940) [46] intro-
 142 duced the so-called *Mendelian algebras* for diploid species. Nevertheless, it
 143 was Ivor Malcolm Haddon Etherington (1908-1994) who, in 1939, introduced
 144 in Genetics [39] the systematic study of commutative non-associative linear
 145 algebras, by describing in particular the following three types of algebras:

- 146 • A *gametic algebra* is a finite-dimensional algebra of basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$
147 such that $e_i \cdot e_j = \sum_k p_{ij}^k e_k$, where each structural constant p_{ij}^k belongs
148 to the real interval $[0, 1]$ so that $\sum_k p_{ij}^k = 1$, for all $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.
149 As such, each value p_{ij}^k represents the probability that an arbitrary
150 gamete of zygotic type e_k derives from an individual of zygotic type
151 $e_i e_j$. As occurs with the QSOs, the probability or progeny distribution
152 describes the evolution of the population under consideration. The
153 latter constitutes a free population if the inheritance process derives
154 from random matings; that is, with absence of sexual differentiation
155 and selection.
- 156 • A *zygotic algebra* is the *duplicate* of a gametic algebra. That is, the
157 former is isomorphic to the set of quadratic forms of the latter.
- 158 • A *copular algebra* is the duplicate of a zygotic algebra.

159 Each one of the three just described algebras are baric by means of the
160 weight ω that is linearly defined from $\omega(e_i) = 1$, for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Here,
161 $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ is the basis of the algebra under consideration, and hence,

$$\omega(e_i)\omega(e_j) = 1 = \sum_k p_{ij}^k = \sum_k p_{ij}^k \omega(e_k) = \omega\left(\sum_k p_{ij}^k e_k\right) = \omega(e_i e_j),$$

162 for all i, j . Further, Etherington called *train algebra* any baric algebra A
163 with weight ω such that the equation of lowest degree relating the principal
164 powers of any vector $x \in A$ has the form

$$x^m + c_1 \omega(x) x^{m-1} + \dots + c_m \omega(x)^m = 0.$$

165 Finally, he termed *special train algebra* any baric algebra A with weight ω
166 such that $N = \ker(\omega)$ is nilpotent (that is, there exists a positive integer
167 $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $N^m = 0$) and all the principal powers N^i , with $i \in \mathbb{N}$, are
168 ideals of A . In particular, every special train algebra is a train algebra.

169 Etherington called *genetic algebra* any one of the family of gametic, zy-
170 gotic and copular algebras and ensured that “*all the fundamental genetic*
171 *algebras are special train algebras*”. Shortly after, he indicated [40] that this
172 statement is only valid for gametic algebras, but not even for zygotic algebras,
173 because the duplicate of a special train algebra, although a train algebra, is
174 not always a special train algebra. This fact provided serious problems for
175 translating some properties and relations from genetic inheritance processes.

176 In order to avoid the flaws in Etherington's genetic algebras and give rise
 177 to a transparent structure theory for them, Richard Donald Schafer (1918–
 178 2014) [88] provided in 1949 an alternative formal definition that is interme-
 179 diate between the concepts of train algebra and special train algebra. To this
 180 end, he made use of the *transformation algebra* $T(A)$ of a non-associative al-
 181 gebra A . It is the algebra of all the polynomials with coefficients in the base
 182 field, whose variables are transformations in the set formed by the identity
 183 map in A , all the *right multiplications* $R_\alpha : A \mapsto A$ such that $R_\alpha(x) = x\alpha$,
 184 and all the *left multiplications* $L_\alpha : A \mapsto A$ such that $L_\alpha(x) = \alpha x$, for all
 185 $\alpha, x \in A$. In particular, the transformation algebra of a baric algebra is baric.

186 Further, unlike Etherington, Schafer assumed the commutativity that is
 187 inherent in any inheritance process and hence, he considered $R_\alpha = L_\alpha$, for
 188 all $\alpha \in A$. Then, he called *genetic algebra* any commutative baric algebra
 189 A such that all the coefficients of the characteristic function $|\lambda I - T|$, with
 190 $T \in T(A)$, only depend on the weight of the algebra. As such, every genetic
 191 algebra is a train algebra and every special train algebra is a genetic algebra.
 192 Moreover, unlike special train algebras, the duplicate of a genetic algebra is
 193 always a genetic algebra.

194 In 1971, Harry Gonshör [47] proved that the concept of genetic alge-
 195 bra proposed by Schafer is equivalent to have a commutative algebra A of
 196 basis $\{e_0, e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ such that $e_i e_j = \sum_k c_{ij}^k e_k$, for all $i, j \in \{0, \dots, n\}$,
 197 where $c_{00}^0 = 1$; $c_{0j}^k = 0$, for all $k < j$; and $c_{ij}^k = 0$, for all $i, j > 0$ and
 198 $k \leq \max\{i, j\}$. This new definition was proved to have significant relevance
 199 in Genetics thanks to the genetic meaning that Holgate [55, 57] gave of du-
 200 plicates and derivations of a genetic algebra. The study of the subspace
 201 $\text{Der}(A)$ of derivations of a genetic algebra A has also been dealt with by
 202 Gonshör [48] himself and also by Roberto Costa [34, 35], Aribano Micali
 203 and Philippe Revoy [69], and, much more recently, by Rasul Ganikhodzhaev,
 204 Farrukh Mukhamedov, Abror Pirnapasov and Izzat Qaralleh [45]. Recall in
 205 this regard that $D \in \text{Der}(A)$ if and only if $D(xy) = D(x)y + xD(y)$, for all
 206 $x, y \in A$. As for any algebra, such a subspace constitutes a Lie algebra.

207 Holgate also introduced [54] both notions of *sex differentiation algebra*
 208 and *dibaric algebra*. The former characterizes the equal division of offspring
 209 between both sexes. More specifically, the sex differentiation algebra is a bi-
 210 dimensional commutative algebra of basis $\{m, w\}$ such that $m^2 = w^2 = 0$ and
 211 $mw = wm = (m + w)/2$. Further, an algebra is called dibaric if it admits
 212 a homomorphism onto the sex differentiation algebra. Holgate proved in
 213 particular that, if A is a dibaric algebra, then its *derived algebra* A^2 is a

214 baric algebra. With the introduction of dibaric algebras, he formalized the
215 original idea of Etherington [39] of treating in a separate way male and female
216 components of the population.

217 Another contribution of Holgate [53] in the theory of genetic algebras
218 was the use of isotopisms of algebras in order to represent algebraically the
219 mutation of genotypes in the inheritance process. Recall in this regard that
220 two n -dimensional algebras A and A' are said to be *isotopic* [1] if there exist
221 three non-singular linear transformations f , g and h from A to A' such that
222 $f(u)g(v) = h(uv)$, for all $u, v \in A$. The triple (f, g, h) is called an *isotopism*
223 (an *isomorphism*, if $f = g = h$; and an *homomorphism*, if besides, the
224 condition of non-singularity is not imposed) between the algebras A and A'
225 (see [43] for a recent survey on the theory of isotopisms). Together with
226 Tania Campos [24], Holgate proved that certain types of zygotic algebras
227 representing chromosome segregation and recombination are isotopic.

228 3. Preliminaries on evolution algebras

229 In order to make this article as self-contained as possible and facilitate
230 a better understanding for the reader, we recall in this section some notions
231 and basic results on evolution algebras that were introduced in the original
232 manuscripts of Tian and Vojtechovsky [93, 98]. To this end, and from now
233 on, let E denote an n -dimensional evolution algebra over a base field \mathbb{K} , with
234 natural basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ and structural constants $p_{ik} \in \mathbb{K}$, for all $i, k \in$
235 $\{1, \dots, n\}$. If the base field \mathbb{K} is the real field, then the evolution algebra
236 is said to be *real*. In such a case, it is said to be *non-negative* if $p_{ik} \geq 0$,
237 for all $i, k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. If, besides, $\sum_k p_{ik} = 1$, for all i , then the real and
238 non-negative evolution algebra is called *Markov evolution algebra*.

239 Every evolution algebra E is non-associative, commutative, flexible (that
240 is, $x(yx) = (xy)x$, for $x, y \in E$); not necessarily power-associative (that is,
241 the subalgebra generated by a single element can not be associative); and
242 preserved by direct sums. Moreover, evolution algebras are not closed under
243 subalgebras. So, a subalgebra of E is called an *evolution subalgebra* if the
244 former is spanned by a subset of generators of the latter. As such, it is an
245 ideal of E . The latter is *indecomposable* if it is not the direct sum of two
246 nonzero ideals; *connected* if it is not the direct sum of two proper evolution
247 subalgebras; *irreducible* if it has no proper subalgebra; and *simple* if it has no
248 proper evolution subalgebra. Tian proved [93, Theorem 9] that any finite-
249 dimensional evolution algebra has a simple evolution subalgebra.

250 Every evolution algebra E is uniquely determined by its *evolution operator*
 251 $L : E \mapsto E$, which is linearly described from

$$L(e_i) := e_i e_i = \sum_i p_{ik} e_k, \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, n\}.$$

252 Then, for each positive integer $m > 2$, it is defined the *plenary power*

$$e_i^{[m]} := L(e_i^{[m-1]}),$$

253 where $e_i^{[0]} := e_i$. The operator L may be considered as time-step in a discrete-
 254 time dynamical system, and hence, it describes the dynamical flow of the
 255 evolutionary process represented by the evolution algebra E . In this regard,
 256 a generator e_i of the evolution algebra E is called *algebraically persistent* if
 257 the evolution subalgebra generated by e_i is a simple evolution subalgebra. As
 258 such, it represents an absorbent state giving rise to a stable evolution. Oth-
 259 erwise, it is said to be *algebraically transient*, which gives rise to a transitory
 260 evolution. The latter would eventually derive to an absorbent state, but only
 261 after certain generations. Any generator of a simple evolution subalgebra is
 262 algebraically persistent. In particular, every finite-dimensional evolution al-
 263 gebra contains an algebraically persistent generator.

264 A connected evolution algebra is simple if and only if all its generators
 265 are algebraically persistent. Tian proved [93, Theorem 11] that, if E is a
 266 connected finite-dimensional evolution algebra, then

$$E = \bigoplus_{j=1}^{n_0} E_{0,j} + B_0,$$

267 where \bigoplus and $+$ denote, respectively, direct sums of either subalgebras or lin-
 268 ear subspaces; each $E_{0,j}$ is a simple evolution subalgebra so that $E_{0,j} \cap E_{0,j'} =$
 269 $\{0\}$, whenever $j \neq j'$; and B_0 is a linear subspace spanned by algebraically
 270 transient generators, which is called *transient space*. Even if B_0 is not an
 271 evolution subalgebra in general, it may be endowed of evolution structure
 272 from E once the multiplication is restricted within B_0 . The previous decom-
 273 position process can inductively be repeated until no transient space arises.
 274 That is, there exist an integer $m > 0$ and a subset $\{n_1, \dots, n_m\} \subset \mathbb{N}$ such
 275 that

$$E = \sum_{i=0}^m \bigoplus_{j=1}^{n_i} E_{i,j},$$

276 where \sum denote direct sum of linear subspaces and each $E_{i,j}$ is a simple
 277 evolution algebra so that $E_{i,j} \cap E_{i,j'} = \{0\}$, whenever $j \neq j'$. Each subset
 278 $\{E_{i,1}, \dots, E_{i,n_i}\}$ constitutes the i^{th} level of a hierarchical structure describing
 279 the dynamical flow of E , which enabled Tian [95] to ensure that “*simple*
 280 *evolution algebras are the basic blocks for building general evolution algebras*”.
 281 Tian dealt in particular with the spectrum of the evolution operator L at the
 282 0^{th} level of this hierarchy, and set out the following problem.

283 **Problem 3.1 ([93]).** *Study the spectrum of the evolution operator of an evo-*
 284 *lution algebra at the i^{th} level of the hierarchical structure of the latter, for each*
 285 *$i > 1$. Furthermore, study the spectrum theory concerning plenary powers of*
 286 *evolution algebras.*

287 Furthermore, the just described hierarchical structure may also be used
 288 to classify evolution algebras. More specifically, evolution algebras can be
 289 distributed according to the number of levels of its related hierarchical struc-
 290 ture and the number of simple evolution subalgebras at each level. Every
 291 evolution algebra is homomorphic to a unique evolution algebra, which is
 292 called its *skeleton-shape*, whose hierarchy has only one-dimensional evolution
 293 algebras in all its levels [93, Theorem 15]. In particular, evolution algebras
 294 within each class of the mentioned distribution are uniquely determined up
 295 to their skeleton-shape homomorphism.

296 Another method for classifying evolution algebras is based on the period
 297 of their generators. In this regard, a generator e_i is said to *occur* in $x =$
 298 $\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i e_i \in E$ if $\alpha_i \neq 0$. It is denoted $e_i \prec x$. The *period* of a generator e_i is
 299 defined as

$$d_i := g.c.d. \left\{ \log_2 m : e_i \prec e_i^{[m]} \right\}.$$

300 If $\left\{ \log_2 m : e_i \prec e_i^{[m]} \right\} = \emptyset$, then $d_i = \infty$. Further, if $d_i = 1$, then the gene-
 301 rator e_i is called *aperiodic*. Otherwise, it is called *periodic*. If the evolution
 302 algebra is non-negative simple, then all its generators have the same period
 303 [93, Theorem 7]. As such, non-negative simple evolution algebras may be
 304 classified as either periodic or aperiodic. In the first case, if $d > 1$ is the period
 305 of all the generators of a non-negative simple evolution algebra E , then these
 306 generators can be partitioned into d disjoint classes C_0, \dots, C_{d-1} such that,
 307 if Δ_i denotes the linear subspace spanned by C_i , for all $i \in \{0, \dots, d-1\}$,
 308 then $L(\Delta_i) \subseteq \Delta_{i+1 \bmod d}$, and

$$E = \bigoplus_{i=0}^{d-1} \Delta_i.$$

309 Based on the already mentioned fact that simple evolution algebras may
 310 be seen as the basic blocks on the hierarchical structure of any evolution
 311 algebra, Tian proposed to generalize the previous results on non-negative
 312 simple evolution algebras. In particular, he set out the following problem.

313 **Problem 3.2 ([95]).** *Delve into the general study of simple evolution al-*
 314 *gebras, and not only non-negative ones. Characterize them and prove the*
 315 *existence of transitive occurrence relations. To this end, study in particular*
 316 *simple evolution algebras over finite fields. Furthermore, it is also required*
 317 *to delve into the study of simple evolution algebras at higher levels of the*
 318 *hierarchy of evolution algebras, and not only at the 0th level.*

319 4. Developing the theory of evolution algebras

320 This section deals with some of the most important results concerning
 321 the mathematical fundamentals of the theory of evolution algebras. Again,
 322 let E denote from now on an n -dimensional evolution algebra over a base
 323 field \mathbb{K} , with natural basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ and structural constants $p_{ik} \in \mathbb{K}$, for
 324 all $i, k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.

325 4.1. Nilpotent evolution algebras

326 In 2013, based on the non-necessary associativity of evolution algebras,
 327 José Manuel Casas, Manuel Ladra, Bakhrom Omirov and Utkir Rozikov [26]
 328 distinguished among nil evolution algebras, right nilpotent evolution algebras
 329 and nilpotent evolution algebras. More specifically, for each vector $x \in E$
 330 and each positive integer $i > 1$, let $x^{<i>} := x^{<i-1>}x$, where $x^{<1>} := x$. Then,
 331 the vector x is *nil* if there exists a positive integer n such that $x^{<n>} = 0$.
 332 The evolution algebra E is *nil* if all its elements are nil. Its *nilindex* is the
 333 minimum positive integer n such that $x^{<n>} = 0$, for all $x \in E$. Further, the
 334 evolution algebra E is *right nilpotent* if $E^{<n>} = 0$, for some positive integer n ,
 335 where $E^{<1>} := E$ and $E^{<k+1>} := E^{<k>}E$, for every positive integer $k > 1$.
 336 Finally, the evolution algebra E is *nilpotent* if $E^n = 0$, for some positive
 337 integer n , where $E^1 := E$ and $E^k := \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} E^i E^{k-i}$, for every positive integer
 338 $k > 1$. The index of (right) nilpotency is defined similarly to the nilindex.

339 In any case, this distinction is not necessary in case of dealing with finite-
 340 dimensional complex evolution algebras. It is so that the mentioned authors
 341 proved [26, Theorem 3.1] the equivalence of right nilpotency and nility for
 342 finite-dimensional evolution algebras. Their equivalence with nilpotency was
 343 shortly after proved by Luisa María Camacho, José Ramón Gómez, Omirov
 344 and Rustam Turdibaev [22, Corollary 4.6] in case of dealing with finite-
 345 dimensional complex evolution algebras. Their structure matrices are all of
 346 them upper triangular after a suitable permutation of their corresponding
 347 natural bases (see also [27, Theorem 2.7]). In any case, it was observed that
 348 the nilindex and the indexes of (right) nilpotency of one such an evolution
 349 algebra do not coincide in general. Further, it was proved [22, Theorem 4.5]
 350 that the maximum index of nilpotency of an n -dimensional evolution algebra
 351 is $2^{n-1} + 1$. A characterization of evolution algebras reaching this maximum
 352 value was described in [26, Theorem 3.6]. More specifically, the index of nilpo-
 353 tency of our evolution algebra E is $2^{n-1} + 1$ if and only if $p_{12}p_{23} \dots p_{(n-1)n} \neq 0$.
 354 The automorphism group and local derivation of these evolution algebras
 355 with maximum index of nilpotency was studied by Mukhamedov, Otabek
 356 Khakimov, Omirov and Qaralleh [71]. Their distribution into isomorphism
 357 classes over the complex field was established in [72].

358 Also in 2013, Ahmed Sadeq Hegazi and Hani Abdelwahab [52] classified
 359 nilpotent evolution algebras of dimension up to three over any base field, and
 360 of dimension four for algebraically closed fields of any characteristic and also
 361 over the real field. To this end, they studied the annihilator extensions of
 362 evolution algebras. Recall here that the *annihilator* of an algebra A is the set
 363 $\text{Ann}(A) = \{x \in A : xy = 0, \text{ for all } y \in A\}$. According to Alberto Elduque
 364 and Alicia Labra [36, Lemma 2.7], the annihilator of the evolution algebra
 365 E is $\text{Ann}(E) = \langle e_i \in A : e_i^2 = 0 \rangle$.

366 In 2014, Tian and Yi Zou [100] characterized nil evolution algebras and
 367 nilpotent evolution algebras in terms of their structural constants. In addi-
 368 tion, they constructed finitely generated nil evolution algebras that are not
 369 nilpotent and explained how their results may be used to model certain pop-
 370 ulation dynamics. They also studied finite-dimensional complex evolution
 371 algebras [22], for which they characterized those nilpotent evolution alge-
 372 bras that are isomorphic to evolution algebras in Jordan normal form. In
 373 2015, Abror Khudoyberdiyev, Omirov and Qaralleh [62] reduced this study
 374 to idempotent and absolute nilpotent elements, whose dynamic in chains of
 375 two-dimensional evolution algebras depending on the time was dealt with by
 376 Sherzod Murodov [74].

377 In 2016, Elduque and Labra [37] distributed into isomorphism classes the
 378 four- and five-dimensional indecomposable nilpotent evolution algebras over
 379 algebraically closed fields of characteristic different from two. One year later,
 380 Abdelwahab Alsarayreh, Qaralleh and Muhammad Ahmad characterized [2]
 381 the space of derivations of three-dimensional nilpotent evolution algebras. In
 382 2018, Camacho, Khudoyberdiyev and Omirov [23] distributed into isomor-
 383 phism classes those nilpotent evolution algebras for which any subalgebra
 384 is an evolution subalgebra. Shortly after, Omirov, Rozikov and María Vic-
 385 toria Velasco [78] distributed into isomorphism classes the set of nilpotent
 386 evolution algebras of dimension $n \leq 5$.

387 4.2. Power-associative evolution algebras

388 Evolution algebras are not necessarily power-associative. Yolanda Ca-
 389 brera, Mercedes Siles and Velasco [17] observed that the evolution algebra
 390 E is power-associative only if $p_{ii}^2 = p_{ii}$, for all i . Thus, every nil evolution
 391 algebra is power-associative [27, Proof of Theorem 2.2]. Examples of nil asso-
 392 ciative evolution algebras, which are therefore power-associative, are shown
 393 in [37]. Further, Luisa María Camacho, José Ramón Gómez, Omirov and
 394 Rustam Turdibaev described [22, Example 4.8] a four-dimensional evolution
 395 algebra that is power-associative, but it is not associative.

396 In 2020, Moussa Ouattara and Souleymane Savadogo proved [79, The-
 397 orem 6] that an evolution algebra is power-associative if and only if it is a
 398 Jordan algebra. They also determined all the power-associative evolution
 399 algebras up to dimension six. The same authors also dealt [80] with the dis-
 400 tribution into isomorphism classes of those indecomposable and not power-
 401 associative evolution nil-algebras up to dimension five, having nil-index four.

402 4.3. Baric evolution algebras

403 Unlike genetic algebras, evolution algebras are not baric in general. In
 404 this regard, Casas, Ladra and Rozikov proved [28, Theorem 3.2] that an
 405 n -dimensional real evolution algebra is baric if and only if there exists a pos-
 406 itive integer $k \leq n$ such that $e_k e_k = p_{kk} e_k \neq 0$. Its weight ω is defined so
 407 that $\omega(\sum_i a_i e_i) = p_{kk} a_i$. Much more recently, Ouattara and Savadogo [80,
 408 Theorem 3.3] have shown that this result can be extended to any commuta-
 409 tive field of characteristic distinct from two. Then, they have also proved [80,
 410 Corollary 3.4] that every baric evolution algebra E over a base field \mathbb{K} admits
 411 a natural basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ and a weight $\omega : E \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ such that $\omega(e_1) = 1$ and
 412 $\omega(e_i) = 0$, for all $i > 1$. Moreover, $E = \mathbb{K}e_1 \oplus \ker(\omega)$, with $e_1 \ker(\omega) = 0$.

413 In this last work, it was also proved the non-existence of evolution train
 414 algebras of rank two [80, Proposition 3.7] and the fact that a baric evolution
 415 algebra of weight ω is a train algebra of rank $r + 1 > 2$ if and only if $\ker(\omega)$
 416 is nil of nil-index r [80, Theorem 3.8]. Moreover, any evolution train algebra
 417 is a special train algebra [80, Theorem 3.12].

418 Casas, Ladra, Omirov and Rozikov proved [26, Theorem 4.1] that finite-
 419 dimensional nilpotent evolution algebras are not dibaric. They also proved
 420 [26, Corollary 4.5] that an evolution algebra is not dibaric when the deter-
 421 minant of its structure matrix is not zero. Finally, they characterized [26,
 422 Proposition 4.10] the two-dimensional real dibaric evolution algebras.

423 4.4. (Semi)simple evolution algebras

424 In 2016, Cabrera, Siles and Velasco established [17, Corollary 4.6] that a
 425 finite-dimensional evolution algebra is simple if and only if its structure ma-
 426 trix associated to a given natural basis is nonsingular and that basis cannot
 427 be reordered so that, for some $m < n$, the structure matrix has block form

$$\begin{pmatrix} W_{m \times m} & U_{m \times (n-m)} \\ 0_{(n-m) \times m} & Y_{(n-m) \times (n-m)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

428 In 2019, Velasco [102, Corollary 3.7] characterized the maximal modu-
 429 lar ideals of an evolution algebra and proved [102, Corollary 3.8] that all of
 430 them have codimension one. Recall in this regard that a *modular ideal* of
 431 the evolution algebra E is any ideal M of the algebra that is endowed with a
 432 *modular unit* $u \in E$ such that $x - xu \in M$, for all $x \in E$. In particular, Ve-
 433 lasco [102, Proposition 2.2] proved that a finite-dimensional evolution algebra
 434 has a unit (and hence, all its ideals are modular) if and only if its structure
 435 matrix associated to a given natural basis is diagonal with non-zero entries.
 436 The intersection of all the maximal modular ideals of the algebra constitutes
 437 its *Jacobson radical*. Then, an evolution algebra is called *semisimple* if its
 438 Jacobson radical is zero. Velasco dealt with semisimple evolution algebras by
 439 introducing the so-called *spectrum* and *m-spectrum* of an evolution algebra.
 440 Both concepts were described in terms of the eigenvalues of a suitable ma-
 441 trix related to the structure matrix of the algebra. She set that the algebra
 442 is *m-semisimple* (respectively, *spectrally semisimple*) if the zero ideal is the
 443 only one for which the *m-spectrum* is $\{0\}$ (respectively, the spectrum is $\{0\}$).
 444 Unlike the associative case (where semisimplicity, spectrally semisimplicity
 445 and *m-semisimplicity* are equivalent), there exist *m-semisimple* evolution al-
 446 gebras whose Jacobson radical coincides with the algebra.

447 *4.5. Perfect evolution algebras*

448 An algebra A is *perfect* if $A^2 = A$. From [36, Theorem 4.4], every perfect
449 evolution algebra has a unique natural basis. (Nadia Boudi, Cabrera and
450 Siles found [13, Corollary 2.7] a condition for an evolution algebra to have
451 a unique natural basis.) Moreover, the automorphism group of a finite-
452 dimensional perfect evolution algebra is finite [36, Theorem 4.8].

453 In 2019, Cabrera, Müge Kanuni and Siles [16] introduced the *basic ideal* of
454 an evolution algebra as an ideal having a natural basis that can be extended
455 to a natural basis of the whole algebra. They established that maximal basic
456 ideals are unique except for those ideals having codimension one. This fact
457 enabled them to ensure [16, Proposition 2.19] that the number of zeros in the
458 structure matrix of an evolution algebra is an invariant, except for those cases
459 in which there exists a maximal basic ideal of codimension one. It is so that
460 the authors showed how maximal basic ideals play a fundamental role in the
461 distribution into isomorphism classes of four-dimensional perfect non-simple
462 evolution algebras. They dealt with this classification over a field with mild
463 restrictions. The complete distribution into isomorphism classes was later
464 studied in [9]. That one of two dimensional perfect evolution algebras over
465 arbitrary fields has recently been established in [25], where it was also studied
466 the automorphism group, the space of derivations and identities of degree at
467 most four of both perfect and non-perfect evolution algebras.

468 In 2020, Boudi, Cabrera and Siles proved [13, Proposition 4.2] that ev-
469 ery nonzero ideal in a perfect evolution algebra is basic. In addition, they
470 observed [13, Corollary 3.8] that a perfect evolution algebra has a nilpotent
471 element of order three only if its structure matrix associated to a given nat-
472 ural basis has a vanishing principal minor. The reciprocal also holds when
473 every element of the base field is a square.

474 In 2021, Elduque and Labra [38, Theorem 4.1] have characterized the
475 space of derivations of any perfect evolution algebra. Particularly, they have
476 proved that, if the characteristic of the base field is zero or two, then this
477 subspace is only formed by the null map. Otherwise, its dimension depends
478 on the number of connected components of a related graph.

479 *4.6. Derivation of evolution algebras*

480 In the previous subsections, we have already mentioned some works con-
481 cerning the study of the space of derivations of different types of evolution
482 algebras. Let us recall here that a *derivation* of the evolution algebra E is
483 any linear map $d : E \rightarrow E$ such that $d(xy) = d(x)y + xd(y)$, for all $x, y \in E$.

484 As for any algebra, the space of derivations of a given algebra is a Lie
 485 algebra that constitutes a good approximation to its automorphism group
 486 and hence, to its algebraic structure. The system of equations describing by
 487 this space was given by Tian himself [93]. More specifically, if d is a derivation
 488 of the evolution algebra E that is described so that $d(e_i) = \sum_k d_{ik}e_k$, with
 489 $d_{ik} \in \mathbb{K}$, for all i , then it must be

$$p_{ik}d_{ji} + p_{jk}d_{ij} = 0, \text{ for all } i, j, k \text{ such that } i \neq j,$$

490 and

$$\sum_k p_{ik}d_{kj} = 2p_{ij}d_{ii}, \text{ for all } i, j.$$

491 It was not until 2013 that Camacho, Gómez, Omirov and Turdibaev [21]
 492 studied formally the space of derivations of n -dimensional complex evolu-
 493 tion algebras depending on the rank of certain matrices. In particular, they
 494 proved that such a subspace is zero for evolution algebras having a non-
 495 singular structure matrix [21, Theorem 2.1]. They also described the space
 496 of derivations of those n -dimensional evolution algebras having a structure
 497 matrix of rank $n - 1$.

498 Much more recently, Paula Cadavid, Mary Luz Rodiño and Pablo M.
 499 Rodríguez [20] described the space of derivations of those evolution algebras
 500 that are uniquely associated with finite simple and connected graphs of order
 501 $n \geq 3$ according to Tian's proposal (see Subsection 5.1). It was observed that
 502 each one of these spaces of derivations depends on the twin partition of the set
 503 of vertices of the corresponding graph. (Recall here that two vertices within a
 504 graph are called *twins* if their neighborhoods coincide.) In particular, if every
 505 part in this twin partition contains at most two vertices, then the space of
 506 derivations is only formed by the null map [20, Theorem 2.3]. The space of
 507 derivations in case of existing some part within this twin partition with at
 508 least three vertices was also characterized [20, Theorem 2.6]. It is remarkable
 509 the fact that the authors dealt with examples of finite-dimensional evolution
 510 algebras having structure matrices of any rank.

511 The same authors, together with Cabrera, have recently explored [15] a
 512 similar extended approach by considering to this end the non-zero entries
 513 of the structure matrix of the evolution algebra under consideration and its
 514 associated directed graph, which had previously been described by Cabrera,
 515 Siles and Velasco [17]. By making use of this approach, the authors have
 516 characterized the derivations of non-degenerate irreducible three-dimensional
 517 evolution algebras.

518 Let us finish this subsection with a proposal of further work on the topic
519 under consideration. Similarly to the relationship between the subset of
520 derivations of an algebra and its automorphism group, there also exists a re-
521 lationship between its *autotopism group* (that is, the group of isotopisms
522 preserving the algebra A under consideration) and its subset of ternary
523 derivations. This terminology was introduced for general algebras by Clara
524 Jiménez-Gestal and José María Pérez-Izquierdo [61]. More specifically, a
525 *ternary derivation* of an algebra A is any triple (d_1, d_2, d_3) of endomorphisms
526 of the algebra such that

$$d_1(xy) = d_2(x)y + xd_3(y),$$

527 for all $x, y \in A$. (See [3] for a comprehensive motivation of this concept.)
528 The following question arises from the important role that isotopisms play
529 as algebraic representations of mutations in Genetics.

530 **Problem 4.1.** *Characterize the subspace of ternary derivations of any given*
531 *finite-dimensional evolution algebra and establish the relationship with its*
532 *autotopism group.*

533 4.7. Classification of evolution algebras

534 In the previous subsections, the distribution into isomorphism classes of
535 different types of evolution algebras has been outlined. Let us indicate here
536 some more results concerning the classification of finite-dimensional evolution
537 algebras.

538 In 2013, Casas, Ladra, Omirov and Rozikov distributed [27, Theorem 4.1]
539 all the two-dimensional evolution algebras over the complex field into six non-
540 isomorphic classes. Nevertheless, Cabrera, Siles and Velasco [18] realized that
541 this classification did not consider the evolution algebra with natural basis
542 $\{e_1, e_2\}$ verifying $e_1^2 = e_2$ and $e_2^2 = e_1$. It was observed when the authors
543 classified those three-dimensional evolution algebras whose derived algebra
544 has dimension two and having annihilator of dimension one [18, Theorem
545 3.5].

546 In 2014, Murodov distributed [73, Theorem 1] into isomorphism classes
547 the set of two-dimensional evolution algebras over the real field. More re-
548 cently, the classification over a general field was independently achieved by
549 Óscar J. Falcón, Raúl M. Falcón and Juan Núñez [41], and by Maria Inez
550 Cardoso, Daniel Gonçalves, Dolores Martín, Cándido Martín and Siles [25].

551 In [41], it was also observed that the distribution of evolution algebras into
552 isotopism classes is uniquely related with the mutation of alleles in non-
553 Mendelian Genetics. In that reference, it was obtained the distribution into
554 four isotopism classes of all two-dimensional evolution algebras, whatever the
555 base field is.

556 In 2017, Cabrera, Siles and Velasco [18] classified into 116 distinct types
557 the set of three-dimensional evolution algebras over any field of characteristic
558 distinct from two and in which there are roots of orders two, three and seven.
559 Their results agreed with those ones of Elduque and Labra [37] concerning the
560 classification of indecomposable nilpotent evolution algebras of dimension up
561 to five over any algebraically closed fields of characteristic distinct from two.
562 More recently, based on an alternative approach, María Eugenia Celorrio and
563 Velasco [31, Theorem 11] classified the mentioned 116 types of algebras into
564 14 non-isomorphic types,

565 In 2018, the distribution of three-dimensional evolution algebras having
566 one-dimensional annihilator was determined in [42, Theorem 4.7], where it
567 was also established [42, Corollary 3.3] the distribution of three-dimensional
568 evolution algebras into isotopism classes, whatever the base field is. This
569 last classification enables one to describe the spectrum of genetic patterns of
570 three distinct genotypes during a mitosis process.

571 Also in 2018, Anvar N. Imomkulov [58] introduced an evolution operator
572 for evolution algebras. Both the set of fixed points and the Jacobian matrix
573 of this operator were studied for two-dimensional evolution algebras. In par-
574 ticular, it was established the distribution into isomorphism classes of those
575 two-dimensional evolution algebras having this Jacobian matrix as structure
576 matrix. The distribution of the three-dimensional case was also dealt with
577 by the same author [59], who proposed as further work the following research
578 problem.

579 **Problem 4.2.** *Study possible approximations of finite-dimensional algebras*
580 *by means of evolution algebras.*

581 A first approach of this problem was considered by Imomkulov himself,
582 together with Rozikov, who determined [60] the relationship among two- and
583 three-dimensional Leibniz algebras and evolution algebras.

584 **5. Relationship to other topics**

585 This section outlines the relationship among evolution algebras, Graph
586 theory, Group theory, Markov chains and Biology.

587 *5.1. Graph theory*

588 In his original manuscript, Tian [93] realized that every finite graph $G =$
589 (V, E) may be associated with an evolution algebra $A(G)$ having the vertex
590 set $V = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ as its natural basis, and such that

$$e_i e_i = \sum_{e_k \in \Gamma(e_i)} e_k,$$

591 for every positive integer $i \leq n$, where $\Gamma(e_i)$ is the neighbourhood of the ver-
592 tex e_i in the graph G . In this way, isomorphic graphs give rise to isomorphic
593 evolution algebras [93, Theorem 41]. Moreover, if

$$L^m(e_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n p_{ik} e_k,$$

594 where L is the evolution operator associated to $A(G)$, then p_{ik} coincides with
595 the total number of paths of length m between both vertices e_i and e_j in the
596 graph G [93, Theorem 43].

597 In order to deal with the reciprocal, Tian [93] introduced the concept of
598 *graphicable algebra* as an evolution algebra of natural basis $V = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$
599 such that

$$e_i e_i = \sum_{e_k \in V_i} e_k,$$

600 for all positive integer $i \leq n$, where $V_i \subseteq V$. Even if evolution algebras are
601 not graphicable in general, every graphicable algebra is uniquely associated
602 to a graph such that $V_i = \Gamma(e_i)$. In this way, two isomorphic graphicable
603 algebras give rise to isomorphic graphs [93, Theorem 42]. In particular, Tian
604 introduced *cycle algebras*, *path algebras* and *complete algebras* as graphicable
605 algebras giving rise, respectively, to cycles, paths and complete graphs. In
606 a similar way, Núñez, María Luisa Rodríguez-Arévalo and María Trinidad
607 Villar [75] dealt with complete tripartite and n -partite, star, friendship, wheel
608 and snark graphicable algebras. These authors also proved [75, Theorem
609 3.8] the existence of graphicable subalgebras within a graphicable algebra.

610 Further, Núñez, Marithania Silvero and Villar dealt [76] with the particular
 611 case of graphicable algebras for which $e_k \in V_i$ if and only if $e_i \in V_k$, and
 612 $e_i \notin V_i$, for every pair of positive integers $i, k \leq n$ such that $i \neq k$. They
 613 called S -graphicable algebras this type of algebras.

614 Based on both notions of evolution algebra arising from a graph and
 615 graphicable algebra, Tian remarked [93] that the ‘*intrinsic and coherent re-*
 616 *lation of evolution algebras with graph theory allows to analyze graphs alge-*
 617 *braically [...] and graph theory may be used as a tool to study non-associative*
 618 *algebras*”. It is so that he asked whether “*every statement or problem in*
 619 *graph theory can be translated into the language of evolution algebras*”. He
 620 put particular interest in the possible relationship of evolution algebras with
 621 random graphs and networks, random walks on graphs, weighted graphs and
 622 directed graphs. Furthermore, Tian also asked for those evolution algebras
 623 arising from finite graphs whose associated Ihara-Selberg zeta function satisfy
 624 the Sunada’s analogue of Riemann hypothesis [91].

625 In 2011, Rozikov and Tian [86] described an alternative for relating an
 626 evolution algebra to a given finite and simple graph by means of state spaces
 627 endowed with Gibbs measures. For connected graphs, they determined the
 628 hierarchical structure of these algebras, together with the dimension and
 629 number of one- and four-dimensional evolution subalgebras [86, Theorem 3.2].
 630 Moreover, all the evolution algebras arising from the same finite and simple
 631 graph, but defined by different Gibbs measures, are pairwise isomorphic [86,
 632 Theorem 3.3]. The authors established as further open problem the study of
 633 the hierarchical structure of evolution algebras associated to graphs that are
 634 either finite, but not connected; or countable and connected.

635 In 2015, Elduque and Labra [36] defined the *directed graph attached* to an
 636 n -dimensional evolution algebra of structure matrix $(p_{ik})_{i,k}$ with respect to a
 637 given natural basis as the graph of set of vertices $V = \{1, \dots, n\}$ and set of
 638 arcs $A = \{(i, k) \in V \times V : p_{ik} \neq 0\}$. If each arc $(i, k) \in A$ is labeled as p_{ik} ,
 639 then one obtains the *directed weighted graph attached* to E . If $\text{Ann}(E) = \{0\}$,
 640 then its directed graph is connected if and only if E does not split into a
 641 direct sum of simple ideals [36, Proposition 2.8]. If the annihilator is not
 642 trivial, then this decomposition is not possible if and only if its directed
 643 graph is connected for every natural basis [36, Proposition 2.10] (see also [17,
 644 Proposition 5.4]). Further, E is nil if and only if its attached directed graph
 645 contains no oriented cycles [36, Theorem 3.4]. These attached (weighted)
 646 directed graphs were also used to distribute into isomorphism classes the set
 647 of four- and five-dimensional nilpotent evolution algebras [37].

648 In 2020, Cadavid, Rodiño and Rodríguez [19] described the evolution
649 algebra induced by the random walk on a graph and studied its relationship
650 with the evolution algebra determined by the same graph according to Tian's
651 proposal [93]. Recall here that the *random walk* on a graph of set of vertices
652 V and adjacency matrix $(a_{ij})_{i,j}$ is a discrete Markov chain with state space
653 V such that the transition probability of moving from state i to state j is

$$p_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sum_{k \in V} a_{ik}}.$$

654 The mentioned authors described the *evolution algebra induced* by this ran-
655 dom walk as the evolution algebra of natural basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ and structure
656 matrix $(p_{ij})_{i,j}$. Then, they studied under which conditions one may ensure
657 that this evolution algebra is isomorphic to Tian's evolution algebra associ-
658 ated to the graph under consideration.

659 Also in 2020, Manuel Ceballos, Núñez and Ángel Tenorio [30] described
660 the *directed weighted pseudograph associated* to an n -dimensional evolution
661 algebra of structure matrix $(p_{ik})_{i,k}$ as the pseudograph resulting after adding
662 a loop on each vertex i of the Elduque and Labra's directed weighted graph
663 attached to E , whenever $p_{ii} \neq 0$. This loop is then labeled as p_{ii} . The
664 distribution into isomorphism classes of these pseudodigraphs enabled them
665 to establish a new classification of evolution algebras.

666 5.2. Group theory

667 Tian [93] associated any given group (G, \circ) having a finite set of genera-
668 tors S with the evolution algebra described over a base field \mathbb{K} so that, for
669 each $g \in G$, one has

$$g \cdot g = \sum_{e \in S} k_e g \cdot e, \tag{1}$$

670 for some $k_e \in \mathbb{K}$. Particularly, Tian set out the following question.

671 **Problem 5.1 ([93]).** *How can the properties of a group be translated to the*
672 *corresponding evolution algebra?*

673 5.3. Markov chains

674 Tian himself [93] realized that every Markov chain is related to a Markov
675 evolution algebra whose structural constants coincide with the transition
676 probabilities of the former and whose basis constitutes the state space of the
677 Markov process.

678 As such, generators of Markov evolution algebras represent states of
679 stochastic processes described by Markov chains, which may, therefore, be
680 studied by means of the theory of evolution algebras. In particular, Markov
681 chains may be classified according to the hierarchies of their corresponding
682 evolution algebras. Tian proved that a Markov chain is irreducible if and
683 only if its related evolution algebra is simple [93, Theorem 18], and that a
684 subset of state space of a Markov chain is probabilistic closed if and only if it
685 generates an evolution subalgebra [93, Theorem 17]. In addition, probabilistic
686 periods in Markov chains are uniquely related to periods of generators in
687 evolution algebras [93, Proposition 10].

688 Tian also introduced the possibility of dealing with *continuous evolution*
689 *algebras*, once structural constants are replaced by differential functions de-
690 pending on a variable. If the latter represents the time, then continuous
691 evolution algebras are uniquely related to continuous-time Markov chains
692 [99]. Tian thought that the study of continuous evolution algebras “*will be*
693 *very interesting because they have a kind of semi-Lie group structure*”.

694 In 2011, as a generalization of Tian’s idea, Casas and Rozikov [28] re-
695 alized that every Markov chain is associated to a *chain of n -dimensional*
696 *evolution algebras* $\{A^{[s,t]}: 0 \leq s \leq t\}$ depending on two time parameters s
697 and t . Their structure matrices $\mathcal{M}^{[s,t]}$ are all of them stochastic and sat-
698 isfy that $\mathcal{M}^{[s,t]} = \mathcal{M}^{[s,\tau]}\mathcal{M}^{[\tau,t]}$, for all $s < \tau < t$. This chain represents a
699 continuous time dynamical system that is an evolution algebra in each fixed
700 time. If all the matrices of the chain coincide, then they constitute the same
701 evolution algebra that Tian associated to a Markov chain. Furthermore, if
702 both time parameters s and t are reduced to only one of them, then the chain
703 is called *time-homogeneous* and is associated to a time-homogeneous Markov
704 chain. The authors also dealt with chains of evolution algebras for which the
705 stochastic condition is removed.

706 In 2013, Rozikov and Mudorov [85] constructed 25 distinct examples of
707 chains of two-dimensional evolution algebras, for which they studied their
708 baricity, nilpotency and idempotency. In 2015, Omirov, Rozikov and Kaisar
709 Tulenbayev [77] dealt with real chains of n -dimensional evolution algebras
710 corresponding to a permutation of n numbers and showed that one such
711 a chain is trivial if and only if the permutation has no fixed points [77,
712 Proposition 1]. Moreover, since every trivial chain of evolution algebras is
713 a chain of nilpotent evolution algebras [77, Proposition 2], they constructed
714 chains of three-dimensional evolution algebras. They also dealt with the
715 construction of arbitrary-dimensional symmetric chains of evolution algebras.

716 In 2017, Ladra and Rozikov [64, 65] described non-homogeneous continu-
717 ous time Markov chains. More recently, Irene Paniello [82] has delved into the
718 algebraic structure of Markov evolution algebras for both the discrete-time
719 and the continuous-time arising from standard stochastic semigroups.

720 5.4. *Biology*

721 Since the original manuscripts of Tian and Vojtechovsky, evolution al-
722 gebras have been implemented in Biology to represent different aspects of
723 non-Mendelian inheritance (particularly, uniparental inheritance) in an alge-
724 braic way. Thus, Tian himself [94] made use of these algebras to analyze how
725 the homoplasmy of a cell population (represented by persistent generators)
726 can derive from an heteroplasmy one (represented by transient generators).
727 This is useful, for instance, to study mitochondrial disorders and mutations
728 in tissues of patients. He also implemented evolution algebras to describe
729 genetically dynamical patterns that provide information about the asexual
730 reproduction of *Phytophthora infestans* causing the late blight of tomatoes
731 and potatoes. An algebraic concept as nilpotency represents the extinction
732 of original genetic types after certain generations.

733 Continuous-time dynamical systems of mosquito populations were studied
734 by Rozikov and Velasco [87]. Mosquito populations were already been dealt
735 with from an algebraic point of view in 2011 by Junliang Lu and Jia Li [66],
736 who proposed a discrete time structured model of such a population. On
737 their own, Rozikov and Velasco considered a discrete-time dynamical system
738 described by an evolution algebra with two fixed points, which become saddle
739 points under some conditions on the parameters of the system. Its structure
740 matrix is equal to the Jacobian of the QSO at a fixed point.

741 Another aspect that Tian [93] realized was the possible use of evolution
742 algebras on *coalescent theory* [97]. That is, on genetic evolution reversely
743 over time. The study of backwards evolution of Mendelian genetic systems
744 by means of coalgebras had been previously introduced in 2004 by Tian and
745 Bai-Lian Li [96]. In 2019, Paniello [81] introduced the concept of *evolution*
746 *coalgebra* in order to model backwards evolution of Non-Mendelian genetic
747 systems. She established the connection between such coalgebras and evolu-
748 tion algebras, by focusing in particular on the cases of genetic realizations.

749 In 2020, Miguel Bustamante, Mellon and Velasco [14] described necessary
750 and sufficient conditions for a given algebra to be an evolution algebra. They
751 proved that this problem is equivalent to the simultaneous diagonalization
752 via congruence of a given set of matrices. Based on this fact, they realized

753 that arbitrarily small perturbations of classical genetic algebras representing
754 Mendelian and auto-tetraploid inheritance (which are not evolution algebras)
755 may give rise to evolution algebras. The algebraic representations of sexual
756 and asexual inheritance by means of genetic and evolution algebras seem,
757 therefore, to be closer than previously thought. A further study of baric
758 and evolution algebras was established by the authors as a first stage to
759 better understand this relationship. In any case, notice that Mukhamedov
760 and Qaralleh already set out the following question in 2014.

761 **Problem 5.2 ([70]).** *Is there a transformation of a given genetic algebra to*
762 *some evolution algebra?*

763 They gave an affirmative answer in case of dealing with two-dimensional
764 genetic algebras (see [70, Theorem 4.1]). The resulting transformation en-
765 abled them to provide necessary conditions on the structure matrix of these
766 genetic algebras for ensuring the existence of non-trivial derivations (see [70,
767 Theorem 5.1]).

768 6. Conclusion

769 This paper has dealt with the past, origin, development and possible
770 further work of the theory of evolution algebras introduced by Tian [92] in
771 2004, with particular emphasis in the relationship that this theory has with
772 a wide amount of distinct branches, not only in Mathematics, but with other
773 areas of research. As such, the paper aims to be a starting point for all those
774 researchers interested in this topic.

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